

SHORT PAPER – CONFERENCE PAPER

Conference Paper Society for the History of War - Potsdam

Nina Janz, NIOD, Amsterdam (n.janz@niod.knaw.nl; drjanz.nina@gmail.com)

Title: Between Sovereignty and Subordination: Small-State Military Engagements in WWII – Belgium and Luxembourg in the Allied War Effort

28 November 2025

This paper examines how smaller occupied countries—especially Belgium and Luxembourg—participated in the Allied coalition during the Second World War. Although the story of Europe’s liberation is usually centred on major actors such as the United States, Britain, and Canada, smaller states also played a role. Their participation is often overlooked because they operated from a position of weakness: their governments were in exile, their territories were under occupation, and their ability to contribute manpower or resources was extremely limited. Yet precisely because their position was so fragile, their involvement sheds important light on how coalition warfare actually functioned when partners were deeply unequal and when the political stakes were extremely high.

For these smaller states, the war was not only about defeating Nazi Germany. It was also about reclaiming a homeland, demonstrating continued independence, and maintaining international visibility while operating entirely from abroad. Joining the Allied coalition therefore carried both military and political meaning: it allowed them to fight, but also to prove that they remained functioning states. This paper explores how Belgium and Luxembourg navigated these challenges and how their contributions were shaped by diplomatic negotiations, organisational constraints, and military realities. It is very much a first step in a new research project begun only a few months ago, and the analysis presented here is preliminary. Fully understanding these dynamics will require several more years of archival work in Belgium, Luxembourg, Britain, and the United States. Nevertheless, early findings already point to important themes.

The first part of the paper considers the broader role of smaller occupied countries in the Allied coalition and the challenges Britain faced in integrating them. At the diplomatic level, questions of trust were constant: communication networks were weak, authority was unclear, and the exiled governments had to negotiate almost everything with London. Organisationally, these states had virtually no resources. They struggled to finance their governments, equip their forces, provide training, and even maintain basic administrative functions. At every stage, they depended heavily on Britain, and sometimes on the United States. This raised the fundamental question of whether their contribution—in terms of manpower, matériel, and political symbolism—was worth the considerable effort required from both sides.

The second part of the paper examines a particularly illustrative issue: recruitment. Belgium’s military collapse in 1940 left it with no functioning army except for small units in the Congo. Luxembourgers, for their part, had no army at all. Rebuilding a force meant relying on volunteers who had escaped occupied Europe or who were living abroad. Belgium attempted to conscript men already in Britain, but numbers were far too small: many Belgians there were working in essential industries or were outside the age limits. As a result, the government expanded recruitment to include Belgians across the world. Files from the Belgian government-in-exile and the British Foreign Office show extensive correspondence about visas, escape routes, and travel arrangements. In some cases, getting a volunteer to Britain could require

extraordinary detours: in 1941, three Belgians in Stockholm were told they could only reach London by travelling via India, and the Belgian government paid the cost.

Once in Britain, volunteers faced security screening, as anyone arriving from occupied Europe was suspected of possibly being a German spy. Nevertheless, Britain gradually relaxed earlier hesitations, especially once the need for manpower became more pressing. In late 1941, Belgium authorised the enlistment of certain non-Belgian volunteers who had strong ties to the country. Although the British foreign and war offices initially feared that admitting foreigners might weaken the Belgian character of the army or pose security risks, Belgian ministers assured them that only people with genuine Belgian links would be accepted. Among these new recruits were Luxembourgers, many of whom had escaped through France or North Africa and sought to continue the fight. A significant number served in Brigade Piron, the 1st Belgian Infantry Brigade, which participated in the liberation of Normandy, Belgium, and the Netherlands. By mid-1944, roughly one hundred Luxembourgers were in the unit, many concentrated in an artillery battery. Their presence highlighted both the practical necessity of broad recruitment and the political solidarity between Belgium and Luxembourg.

The political dimension was equally important. Belgium and Luxembourg were not simply asking Britain for support; they were trying to rebuild state institutions from exile while maintaining internal unity. Within the Belgian forces, deep political divisions existed between supporters and critics of King Leopold III. Reports of low morale, disciplinary disputes, and accusations of mismanagement reached both London and Brussels. Britain thus found itself needing to coordinate not only military matters, but also complex internal politics among its exile partners.

Britain's formal framework for managing these relationships developed during the war. After initial British scepticism—rooted partly in frustration over Belgium's surrender in 1940—the needs of the wider Allied coalition prompted a more supportive approach. The Allied Forces Act of August 1940 legally permitted foreign armies to operate on British soil. The Anglo-Belgian Armed Forces Agreement of September 1941 allowed Belgian troops to retain their own officers, symbols, and command structure, while adopting British methods for training, uniforms, and equipment. A revised agreement in 1942 promised closer consultation with Belgium about the deployment of its troops and even gave access to British naval resources. Meanwhile, the Allied Powers (War Service) Act of August 1942 introduced compulsory enlistment for eligible Allied nationals in Britain, formalising their military obligations while keeping strategic control in British hands.

By 1944, the Forces Belges de Grande-Bretagne included around 7,000 personnel across land, air, and naval branches, with roughly 1,200 killed in action. Their significance was not primarily numerical; rather, these forces symbolised Belgium's uninterrupted participation in the Allied struggle and strengthened its claim to stand among the victors in 1945. Luxembourg, despite lacking a pre-war army, similarly used its cooperation with Britain and the United States—through political agreements and participation in exile forces—to restore its international position.

The experience of Belgium and Luxembourg shows that coalition warfare was more than just military coordination. It involved political reconstruction, symbolic affirmation, and intense negotiation—especially when partners operated from exile and depended entirely on others for resources, training, and legitimacy. Their participation was both a necessity and an act of

national self-assertion. Even while fighting for survival, they were rebuilding the institutional and diplomatic foundations that would anchor them in the post-war European order.

Looking forward, this project will investigate the role of military diplomacy in shaping post-war arrangements. Liaison officers and inter-allied networks, in particular, offer a promising angle for understanding how cooperation worked on a day-to-day basis. As this research is still in its early stages, further archival work will be essential to build a fuller picture of how small states operated within—and helped shape—the Allied coalition.

*Selected Bibliography**

Allen, Robert W. “Britain Revives the Belgian Army 1940–45.” *Journal of Strategic Studies* 21, no. 4 (1998): 78–96.

Bernardo y Garcia, Luis Angel, and Geertrui Elaut. *Belgium in Exile 1940–1944: Gouvernement belge, réfugiés et soldats en Grande-Bretagne. Exposition: Bruxelles, Archives générales du Royaume, 9 décembre 2010 au 3 avril 2011. Catalogue.* Archives générales du Royaume et Archives de l’État dans les provinces, 2010.

Bottelier, Th. W. “‘Not on a Purely Nationalistic Basis’: The Internationalism of Allied Coalition Warfare in the Second World War.” *European Review of History* 27, nos. 1–2 (2020): 152–75. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13507486.2019.1705251>.

Bud, G. C. P. “‘The Sanctuary of Them All’: The Politics of Manpower and Nationality in the Armies in Exile in the United Kingdom, 1940–4.” *Historical Research* 97, no. 276 (2024): 259–79. <https://doi.org/10.1093/hisres/htad035>.

Conway, Martin. “15. Legacies of Exile: The Exile Governments in London during the Second World War and the Politics of Post-War Europe.” In *Europe in Exile*, edited by Martin Conway and José Gotovitch. Berghahn Books, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781782389910-016>.

De Vos, Luc. “5. The Reconstruction of Belgian Military Forces in Britain, 1940–1945.” In *Europe in Exile*, edited by Martin Conway and José Gotovitch. Berghahn Books, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781782389910-006>.

Deloge, Pascal. “6. Belgian Military Plans for the Post-War Period.” In *Europe in Exile*, edited by Martin Conway and José Gotovitch. Berghahn Books, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781782389910-007>.

Fédération des anciens combattants de la Brigade Piron and Comité 44-94. *Belgian Forces in United Kingdom.* Comité 44-94 (Oostende); Fédération des anciens combattants de la Brigade Piron (Bruxelles), 1994. SYRACUSE. <https://opac.kbr.be/Library/doc/SYRACUSE/16815743/belgian-forces-in-united-kingdom>.

Wenkin, Hugues. *Les moutons noirs de Piron!* Weyrich (Neufchâteau), 2017. SYRACUSE. <https://opac.kbr.be/Library/doc/SYRACUSE/18335220/les-moutons-noirs-de-piron>.

Wilkin, Bernard, and Bob Moore. *Escaping Nazi Europe: Understanding the Experiences of Belgian Soldiers and Civilians in World War II.* Routledge Studies in Second World War History. Routledge, 2024. WorldCat.

National Archives, Kew. Series: Foreign Office and War Office.

* The literature review and archival research are ongoing and not yet complete at this stage.